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Bioprospecting of endophytes in medicinal plants for antifungal properties against *Candida albicans* (C.P.Robin) Berkhout – case study of *Mitracarpus scaber* Zucc. (Rubiaceae)

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ABSTRACT

Endophytic fungi are microorganisms that inhabit the living tissues of their host plants without causing harm to the host plant. They are a promising source of bioactive compounds with antimicrobial properties. This study investigated the antifungal activity of extracts of endophytic fungi (*Aspergillus nidulans* and *Fusarium oxysporum*) against *Candida albicans* conducted at the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Bayero University, Kano, Nigeria. The sample was collected at the Botanical Garden, Bayero University, Kano. The antifungal properties were tested using the agar well diffusion method (1.0 mg/mL, 0.5 mg/mL, 0.25 mg/mL, 0.125 mg/mL, 0.625 mg/mL) for two different solvents, with Fluconazole as the positive control and distilled water as the negative control. The data was collected, and inhibition zones were determined. The result shows a dose-dependent increase in antifungal activity, with the highest inhibition zone observed at 1.0 mg/mL. Statistical analysis was conducted using ANOVA at $P < 0.05$. There was a significant difference between the concentrations and extracts ($P < 0.01$).

Keywords: Endophytic fungi, antifungal activity, *Aspergillus*, *Fusarium*, *Candida albicans*, Dose-dependent Response, Fluconazole

1. INTRODUCTION

Fungal infections have emerged as a significant global concern, particularly due to the increasing prevalence of opportunistic pathogens such as *Candida albicans* (Pappas et al., 2018). As a commensal organism, *Candida albicans* is normally present in the human microbiota, which can be pathogenic under certain conditions, leading to localized and systemic infections. These infections range from superficial candidiasis (e.g, oral thrush and vaginal candidiasis) to life-threatening invasive candidiasis that has high morbidity and mortality rates with severe cases reported in individuals with weakened immune systems such as HIV/AIDS patients, cancer patients undergoing chemotherapy, individuals with diabetes, and organ transplant recipients on immunosuppressive therapy (Lee et al., 2021). The treatment of *C. albicans* infections primarily relies on antifungal drugs, including azoles (e.g, fluconazole), polyenes (e.g., amphotericin B), etc. However, the increasing resistance of *C. albicans* to these conventional antifungal agents has become a significant clinical challenge (Akbar et al., 2025). Azole resistance in particular has been widely documented due to the overuse of fluconazole in both clinical and agricultural settings (Rodriguez-Tudela et al., 2020; White et. al., 1997; Yassien et al., 2015). The emergence of drug-resistant strains of *C. albicans* has led to treatment failures, prolonged hospital stays, and increased mortality rates, necessitating the urgent search for alternative antifungal compounds with a novel mechanism of action (Astvad et al., 2017; Akbar et al., 2025). Natural products, particularly those derived from microorganisms, have long served as a valuable reservoir of bioactive compounds with significant pharmaceutical potential. Endophytic fungi, which live asymptotically within plant tissues, have emerged as a focal point of interest due to their ability to produce novel secondary metabolites with diverse biological activities (El-Sayed et al., 2023; Gunatilaka, 2006; Kusari et al., 2012). These fungi form a symbiotic relationship with their host plants, often synthesizing compounds that bolster plant defense against pathogens. Research has the capacity to generate antimicrobial, antiviral, anticancer, and immunomodulatory agents, positioning them as promising candidates for the discovery of new antifungal therapies (Deshmukh et al., 2018; El-Sayed et al., 2024; Newman & Cragg, 2020). Among the various genera of endophytic fungi, *Aspergillus* and *Fusarium* species stand out for their extensive production of secondary metabolites with notable bioactivity. *Aspergillus nidulans*, for example, is recognized for synthesizing polyketides, alkaloids, and terpenoids, which exhibit antifungal and antibacterial properties (Bachmann et al., 2021). Despite these capabilities, the specific antifungal properties of endophytic *Aspergillus nidulans* and *Fusarium oxysporum* pathogenic yeast remain insufficiently explored.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Study area

The leaves of healthy *Mitracarpus scaber* were harvested within the premises of Bayero University Kano, Kano State, Nigeria, located at the latitude of 11.98 N.

2. 2. Place and time

The study was conducted at the Microbiology Laboratory of the Department of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bayero University, Kano, and was held from November 2024 to March 2025.

2. 3. Materials

Materials used in this study include the leaves of *Mitracarpus scaber*, Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA), Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB), Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA), and *Candida albicans* fungi. Organic solvents used include ethyl acetate.

2. 4. Isolation of endophytic fungi

Isolation of the endophytic fungi was carried out according to Rumidatul et al. The leaves were cut approximately 1 cm long and rinsed with distilled water for surface sterilization and then sequentially washed with 70% ethanol for 1 minute, 2% sodium hypochlorite for 5 minutes, and rinsed with distilled water to remove any remaining chemicals. The leaves were cut and placed on Potato Dextrose Agar medium and incubated at 28 °C for seven days, and sub-cultured for 14 days to obtain a pure isolate, and were identified.

2. 5. Fermentation of fungal endophytes and extraction of products of fermentation

This was carried out using the method of Akpotu et al. (2021) with a little modification. Briefly. The pure fungal isolates were cultivated on Potato Dextrose Broth (PDB) by placing 4 agar blocks of pure culture (10 mm in diameter) of actively growing culture in a 250 ml flask containing 100 ml of the medium. The flask was incubated in a shaker condition for 3 weeks (21 days) at 27 °C.

Figure 1. Filtration of culture broth.

The culture was filtered through filter paper to remove the mycelial mats. The liquid broth was collected and extracted with an equal volume of ethyl acetate in a separating funnel by shaking vigorously for one hour. The cell mass was separated and weighed to obtain the weight of the mycelium. The solvent was evaporated, and the resultant compound was dried and concentrated to yield the crude extract.

2. 6. Phytochemical analysis of the extract

Phytochemical components of the endophytic extract crude extracts were analyzed qualitatively. The phytochemical constituents screened for were saponins, carbohydrates, tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, anthraquinones, cardiac glycosides, terpenoids, steroids, and triterpenes (Namadina M. M. et al., 2024).

2. 6. 1. Test for saponins: frothing test

About 10 milliliters of distilled water were combined with a portion of the extract, and the mixture was vigorously shaken for 30 seconds. The tube was kept upright and monitored for half an hour. A honeycomb foam that persisted for ten to fifteen minutes demonstrated the presence of saponins

2. 6. 2. Test for carbohydrates Molish's (General) Test for carbohydrates

To 1 ml of the filtrate, 1 ml of Molish's reagent was added in a test tube, followed by 1 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid down the test tube to form a lower layer. A reddish color at the interfacial ring indicated the presence of carbohydrate.

2. 6. 3. Test for tannins Ferric chloride test

3-5 drops of ferric chloride solution were added to the portion of the extract. A greenish black precipitate indicates the presence of condensed tannins, while hydrolysable tannins give a blue or brownish blue precipitate

2. 6. 4. Test for flavonoids

A portion of the extract was treated with a few drops of NaOH. Formation of intense yellow color that became colorless on addition of a few drops of dilute HCL confirmed the presence of flavonoids.

2. 6. 5. Test for alkaloids Wagner's Test

A few drops of Wagner's reagent were added to a portion of the extract, and a whitish precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

2. 6. 6. Test for anthraquinones Borntrager's test

Exactly 5 ml of chloroform was added to the portion of the extract in a dry test tube and shaken for 5 mins. This was filtered, and the filtrate shaken with an equal volume of 10% ammonium solution, A bright pink color in the aqueous upper layer indicated the presence of free anthraquinones.

2. 6. 7. Test for cardiac glycosides Kella-Killiani's test

A portion of the extract was dissolved in 1 ml of glacial acetic acid containing traces of ferric chloride solution. This was then transferred into a dry test tube, and 1ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was added down the side of the test tube to form a lower layer at the bottom. Interphase for the purple-brown ring was carefully observed, which indicates the presence of deoxy sugar, and a pale green color in the upper acetic acid layer indicated the presence of cardiac glycosides.

2. 6. 8. Test for terpenoids Salkowski test

To about 3 ml of the filtrate, about 1 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid was carefully added on the side of the test tube to form a layer. Formation of a reddish brown ring at the interface was observed, which shows positive results for the presence of terpenoids.

2. 6. 9. Test for steroids and triterpenes Liebermann-Burchard's test

Equal volumes of acetic acid anhydride were added to the portion of the extract and mixed gently. Concentrated sulphuric acid (1 ml) was added down the side of the test tube to form a lower layer. A color change observed immediately and later indicates the presence of steroids and triterpenes. Red, pink, or purple color indicates the presence of triterpenes, while blue or blue-green indicates Steroids.

2. 7. Identification of endophytic fungi

Endophytic fungi were cultivated for 10 days at 28 ± 2 °C. Fungal isolates were identified morphologically using microscopic examination at the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology, Bayero University, Kano. Colony growth rate and appearance, along with its microscopic features like hypha characteristics, conidium formation, and other cellular bodies such as fruiting bodies (asexual or sexual spores) or structures, were observed using a microscope at a magnification of 400. (Hemeda et al. 2022)

2. 8. Determination of antifungal Susceptibility Testing

2. 8. 1. Source of test organism

Candida albicans isolated was collected from the Microbiology Laboratory, Bayero University Clinic, Old Site, Kano, Nigeria. And was stored in the fridge till the Antifungal activity test is carried out.

2. 8. 2. Agar well diffusion assay

The antifungal activity of the endophytic fungal extracts was evaluated using the agar well diffusion method, a widely used technique for assessing antimicrobial potential (Balouiri et al., 2016; Valgas et al., 2007). A spore suspension of *Candida albicans* was prepared following standard microbial protocol. Sabouraud Dextrose Agar (SDA) was used as the growth medium, ensuring optimal growth conditions for the test organism. One milliliter of the prepared spore suspension of the fungus is placed onto the appropriately labelled petri dish containing the medium. A sterile swab was used to evenly distribute the suspension across the solidified agar surface, ensuring uniform fungal growth (Sasidharan et al., 2011). The plates

were then allowed to dry for 5 minutes before wells (1 cm in diameter) were created using a sterile Cork borer. Each well was loaded with 100 μ L of the test endophytic extract. The plates were incubated at 30 °C for 48 hours. Antifungal activities were determined by measuring the diameter of the inhibition zone around each well, indicating microbial susceptibility to the test extract (Andrews, 2001).

Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) was used as the negative control to rule out solvent effects, while fluconazole was used as the positive control for antifungal activity (Rumidatul et al., 2021). All results were recoded as mean values from three replicates (\pm standard deviation) to ensure reproducibility and accuracy.

2. 9. Statistical analysis

All Statistical analyses were conducted using Microsoft Excel. The mean and standard deviation (SD) of the zone of inhibition (ZOI) were calculated for each concentration of the endophytic fungal extracts. A one-way analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was performed, and all results were visualized using Bar charts, and the Level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A total of five (5) endophytic fungi were isolated from the leaves of *Mitracarpus scaber*, namely *Aspergillus* spp., *Fusarium* spp., *Rhizoctonia* spp., and *Curvularia* spp. Morphological identification was carried out based on colony characteristics and microscopic features; however, molecular identification was not performed, which is acknowledged as a limitation of this study.

Figure 2. Microscopic identification of endophytic fungi.

Figure 3. Physical Identification of endophytic fungal spores.

Phytochemical screening was conducted on extracts from two isolates (*Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp.) that exhibited the highest antifungal potential. As shown in Tables 1 and 2, both extracts contained a range of bioactive compounds such as saponin, carbohydrate, tannin, flavonoids, alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids, and cardiac glycosides. These secondary metabolites were known to contribute to the antimicrobial activity, although the analysis in this study was done qualitatively (+/-).

Table 1. Phytochemical screening of the extract of *Aspergillus* spp. isolated from *Mitracarpus scaber*

S/N	Phytochemicals	<i>Aspergillus</i> extract
1	Saponin	+
2	Carbohydrate	+
3	Taninns	+
4	Flavanoid	+
5	Alkaloid	-
6	Anthraquinones	-
7	Cardiac glycosides	+

8	Terpenoids	-
9	Steroids	+
10	Triterpenes	+

Key: + represents the presence of phytochemical, while – represents the absence of phytochemical

Table 2. Phytochemical screening of the extract of *Fusarium* spp. isolated from *Mitracarpus scaber*.

S/N	Phytochemicals	<i>Fusarium</i> extract
1	Saponin	+
2	Carbohydrate	-
3	Taninns	+
4	Flavanoid	+
5	Alkaloid	+
6	Anthraquinones	+
7	Cardiac glycosides	+
8	Terpenoids	+
9	Steroids	+
10	Triterpenes	+

Key: + represents the presence of phytochemical, while – represents the absence of phytochemical.

The antifungal activities of the endophytic fungal extracts against *Candida albicans* were determined using the agar well diffusion method. Results of the inhibitory zone diameters (IZD) for extracts dissolved in water are shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3. The Inhibitory zone Diameter of Endophytic fungi extract dissolved in DMSO against *Candida albicans*.

Concentrations (mg/ML)	IZD for <i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	IZD for <i>Fusarium</i> spp.
1	18.5±0.5	20.3±0.26

0.5	14.2±0.26	16.5±0.3
0.25	10.8±0.26	12.7±0.21
0.125	8.5±0.2	9.8±0.26
0.0625	6.2±0.1	7.3±0.1
DMSO	0	0
Fluconazole	27	27

Key: values are presented as mean ± Standard deviation. IZD: Inhibitory Zone Diameter.

Table 4. The Inhibitory zone Diameter of Endophytic fungi extract dissolved in distilled water (H₂O) against *Candida albicans*.

Concentrations (mg/ML)	IZD for <i>Aspergillus</i> spp.	IZD for <i>Fusarium</i> spp.
1	16.4±0.4	18.3±0.25
0.5	12.5±0.25	14.8±0.25
0.25	9.8±0.25	11.2±0.25
0.125	7.4±0.21	8.5±0.2
0.0625	5.6±0.1	6.3±0.1
DMSO	0	0
Fluconazole	27	27.5

Key: values are presented as mean ± Standard deviation. IZD: Inhibitory Zone Diameter.

Across all tested concentrations (1 mg/mL to 0.0625 mg/mL), *Fusarium* spp. extracts consistently demonstrated higher antifungal activity compared to *Aspergillus* spp. For instance, at 1 mg/mL in DMSO, the inhibition zone for *Fusarium* spp. was 20.3 ± 0.26 mm, while *Aspergillus* spp. produced 18.5 ± 0.5 mm. A similar trend was observed in aqueous extracts, where *Fusarium* spp. also produced larger inhibition zones than *Aspergillus* spp.

The antifungal effect was concentration-dependent: inhibition zones decreased with progressive dilution, showing clear dose–response activity. This finding is consistent with earlier studies (Bacon & White, 2000; Akpotu et al., 2021) reporting that higher extract concentrations yield stronger antifungal activity. The solvent used also had a notable impact. Extracts prepared in DMSO exhibited significantly greater IZDs than those prepared in distilled water at equivalent concentrations. This aligns with previous reports (Hashem et al., 2022) showing that DMSO enhances the solubility and activity of bioactive metabolites, thereby improving antifungal efficacy.

Overall, the results indicate that *Fusarium* spp. extract possesses stronger antifungal activity than *Aspergillus* spp. extract. The presence of diverse phytochemicals, including tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, and terpenoids, likely contributes to the observed activity. However, it is important to note that only qualitative phytochemical data were obtained, and no additional solvent controls beyond DMSO were tested, which limits interpretation. Future studies should include molecular identification of isolates and quantitative phytochemical analysis to validate and expand on these findings.

4. CONCLUSION

This study shows that endophytic fungal extracts, especially those from *Aspergillus* spp. and *Fusarium* spp., have promising antifungal properties against *Candida albicans*. These findings demonstrated a concentration-dependent inhibition, emphasizing the impact of solvent types on bioactivity. DMSO extract often showed larger zones of inhibition in comparison to water extracts. At greater doses, the extracts had the strongest antifungal activity among those tested, matching that of the common antifungal medication fluconazole. This result implies that endophytic fungi are useful producers of bioactive secondary metabolites and could be used as supplementary or alternative treatments for fungal infections.

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